

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Nidamudin Adam**FIRST NAME:** Kafi**PROGRAM CODE:** ACA-401D**COURSE CODE:** DCCS**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **When developing the research methodology chapter, what are the three main aspects that researchers need to clarify in the chapter?**
 - (1) How was the quality of the information ensured? (2) What was the population size? (3) What was the role of the researcher in the assessment?
 - (1) **What decisions and actions have been taken? (2) Why were the decisions and actions taken? (3) How were the decisions implemented?**¹
 - (1) Who was interviewed? (2) What kind of data was collected? (3) How was the data analyzed?
 - (1) What were the instruments used for data collection? (2) Were the instruments pilot-tested for clarity and use? (3) What were the ethical considerations to ensure that no harm would be inflicted on the participants resulted from participation?

¹ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* by Philip Adu, Ph.D., 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

2. **Which of the statements is correct about research questions?**
- "What must we understand before we know what to do?" is a practical question.
 - "What should we think?" is a conceptual question.²**
 - "What should we do?" is an applied question.
 - None of the above.
3. **What are the four fundamental issues you need to consider when developing the methodology section of your research?**
- Consider the data, problem, research question, and purpose.³**
 - Consider the problem, purpose, literature available, and participants.
 - Consider the research question, problem, audience, and recommendations.
 - Consider the participants, time, data, and problem.
4. **Why should researchers bother to mention the source of information?**
- To prevent severe academic offenses with real consequences.
 - To be fair and give credit for someone else's work.
 - To stay away from plagiarism, which is wrong and unethical.
 - All of the above.⁴**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*, revised by Booth Weyn C. et al., Eighth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 17.

³ Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* by Philip Adu, Ph.D.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

5. **When identifying sources for literature review, the researcher spends much time perusing through the sources to consider. Which of the following is not correctly stated about the sources of information?**

- Primary sources are the best option to use for evidence and literature review.
- Primary sources are formulated from in-depth and critical analysis and interpretation of several abstracts, indexes, reviews, encyclopedia, and textbooks.⁵**
- Secondary sources provide refined analysis and additional documents relevant to the study.
- Secondary sources should be read for knowledge increase but not for presenting evidence in academic research.

6. **When is the use of qualitative approach used?**

- A qualitative approach is used when exploring, explaining, understanding, and collecting participants' stories and perceptions.⁶**
- A qualitative approach is used when exploring a phenomenon, explaining a process, and testing a hypothesis.
- A qualitative approach is used when collecting participants' reviews, describing issues numerically, and exploring complex issues.
- A qualitative approach is used when conducting desk reviews, explaining situations in the natural setting, understanding cases and behaviors, and conducting probability sampling.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*, 24; Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 50.

⁶ Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* by Philip Adu, Ph.D.

7. **When converting a pdf document into a regular document in Zotero, what kind of information can the software's automatic metadata retrieval option provide quickly?**
- It can quickly provide the full information necessary for a citation, including the document type, title, authors, publications dates, and URL.
 - It can quickly provide only the title of the document and year of publication.
 - It can quickly provide some information that should be cross-checked for corrections.⁷**
 - None of the above.
8. **Tables can easily present a large number of similar information in a summarized format. Which of the following statements is not correct on the use of tables?**
- If table information is from a published source, notes that apply to the table as a whole are not numbered.
 - Footnotes are not allowed to explain table contents.⁸**
 - Tables should not be divided across two pages.
 - Chicago style allows the use of symbols such as "%" or "&" in column headings.
9. **Capitalization follows three forms; full caps, heading caps, or sentence caps. When using heading caps, which of the following statements is not correct?**

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck, *ACA-401D Period 2: Zotero Training 02*, accessed February 9, 2021, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>.

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 52; Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*, 219.

- Capitalize articles, prepositions, conjunctions, and infinitives.⁹**
- Capitalize the first letter of a sentence and all nouns.
- Capitalize all first characters after a colon.
- Capitalize all of the above.

10. **Which of the following statements is not correct about long quotations?**

- Long quotations can continue on the same text line as long as you do not use a semicolon.¹⁰**
- Any quotation longer than four lines is a block quotation.
- Long quotations do not need quotation marks (" ").
- Long quotations are used when there is strong language in the quote that can emphasize the meaning very well.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 45.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 7.

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- Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study by Philip Adu, Ph.D.*, 2016. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.
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- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.